

Invited Letter: Welcome to the Journal of Advanced Technological Education

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Welcome to the Journal of Advanced Technological Education!

As the Lead Program Director of the National Science Foundation's Advanced Technological Education Program (ATE), I am pleased to introduce the Journal of Advanced Technological Education (J ATE) to the technician education community. Technician Education programs at two-year Community and Technical Colleges across the United States now have a peer-reviewed journal to learn about the newest advancements in technician education produced and reviewed by their peers.

J ATE covers two-year community and technical colleges with technician education programs in advanced technology industries. These industries include: Micro- and Nano-technologies, Biotechnologies, Autonomous Technologies, Advanced Manufacturing, Cyber Security, Environmental Technologies, Energy, Engineering and the shared technician education space such as mentoring and evaluation. J ATE is a peer-reviewed journal for all Advanced Technological Education (ATE) faculty.

The Micro Nano Technology Education Center (MNT-EC), the national Center for Micro and Nano Technician Education MNT-EC proposed a peer-reviewed Journal as one of their activities Center activities. Since then, the Journal has grown to encompass all sub-disciplines under the ATE umbrella. In addition to community college faculty and staff, the Journal welcomes submission from students doing undergraduate research and industry members involved with community colleges and K-12 teachers and administrators.

My publishing journey started when I was a technician and was given the opportunity to lead and carry out a research project characterizing viral mutations. I continued publishing as a graduate student, post-doctoral fellow, and published during my tenure as a community college faculty. Publishing provides a way for the greater STEM community to be aware of advances made both in research and teaching. The advances made at two-year community and technical colleges often remain either at the institution or, at best, within the region where the institution is located.

I highly recommend two-year faculty, staff, and students publish in J ATE for multiple reasons. These includes knowledge sharing, professional advancement, collaboration opportunities, and dissemination of results that can impact faculty and students at community and technical colleges across the United States.

I am proud to support technician education, the ATE grant program and J ATE. You can support J ATE by submitting articles, serving as a peer reviewer and reading and sharing articles with your colleagues.

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